

Density functional and frontier orbital study of the physical process of the conformational isomerism of ethane[†]

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In order to explore effective theoretical parameters to follow the physical processes of the conformational isomerism, a density functional and molecular orbital study of the conformational isomerism of ethane molecule is furnished by adopting the geometry optimization technique, GOT. The total energy, the eigen values of the frontier orbitals, the HOMO-LUMO gap, the global hardness, the global softness and chemical potential have been computed as a function of torsional angles of the internal rotation of the molecule. The eigen values of the frontier orbitals, the HOMO-LUMO gap, the global hardness and global softness are found to follow the physical process of evolution of the molecular conformations due to unrestricted rotation around single bonds in a molecule. A comparative study of the nature of the profiles of the eigen values of the frontier orbital and the density functional parameters with the potential energy diagram explores the potential ability of the molecular orbital and density functional parameters to study and compute the physical process of the conformational isomerism of the molecule.

A chemical system is a collection of nuclei and electrons. The shape or structure of a molecular polyhedra arises from the arrangement of the nuclei in space and the electron density around such nuclei following the principle of maximum stability or minimum energy. While classifying into various point groups, the molecules are pictured as having rigid and time invariable structures. But the reality of molecular architecture is far from this static picture. The shapes of the molecules evolves continuously with time because of the fast intra-molecular motions arising out of the normal modes of vibrations and rotation around one or more single bonds. A molecule executes continuous vibrations according to its normal modes during which the bond angles and bond lengths are continually changing. In addition to the above vibrational motions, one part of a molecule may undergo continuous rotation with respect to other part around one or more single bonds. The dynamics of the two intra-molecular movements entail an infinite number of momentary arrangements of nuclei (atoms) in space. Each such momentary arrangement of atoms in space has definite energy and is called coformation. The conformations generated by rotation about bonds of chain are conveniently treated in terms of discrete rotational states, generally chosen to coincide with minima in the rotational potential¹. It, therefore, eventually transpires that the term conformations of a molecule means the infinite number of momentary arrangements of atoms in space produced by rotation about single bonds.

The molecular conformations differ from one another in degree of rotation around one or more single bonds (dihedral angles) and in some cases bond lengths and bond angles. The conformations are basically stereoisomers and are distinct molecular species separated by energy barriers and are, in principle, separable at low temperatures and are certainly detectable and observable by physical methods. The phenomenon of generation of continuous conformational isomers through a physical process of continuous evolution of molecular structure following the intramolecular dynamics of unrestricted rotation around one or more single bonds establishes a dynamic equilibrium between a number of energy preferred conformations of the non-rigid molecules. Most of the molecules exist in one or more potential minimum conformations at ordinary temperature, despite their being infinite number of conformations accessible through internal rotation of small energy barrier. The conformation has a critical effect on bio-activity and reactivity on the stereochemical outcome of many reactions, and an understanding of relative energies and conformation populations will enable more reasonable predictions concerning reactivity, stereochemistry, and product distribution in reaction². The conformational analysis is the study of physical and chemical properties of compounds in terms of geometry and populations of various conformations of the pertinent ground state, transition states, and excited states and as such, the study has been an ever enticing and exciting chapter of physical

[†]The paper is dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri.

organic chemistry. One enters the realm of dynamic stereochemistry from the realm of static stereochemistry when dynamic structural isomerism is relied upon to correlate the chemical and physical properties and reactivity of compounds³. The origin of the barrier to internal rotation within a molecule is of interest to theoretical, experimental, and biological chemists. The majority of work in this field until the early 1960's had gone into the experimental determination of barriers⁴.

The most widely studied chemical system in connection with the study of conformational analysis and elucidation of the origin of barrier to internal rotation is ethane, $\text{H}_3\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$. Kemp and Pitzer⁵ discovered that the relative rotation of the two methyl groups about carbon-carbon single bond in ethane is not completely free but is restricted by a potential barrier of about 3 kcal mol^{-1} high, with three maxima and three minima in a complete rotation corresponding to the trigonal symmetry of the methyl group. Since then, rotation barriers in a large number of molecules have been measured and a plethora of information have appeared on the theoretical as well as experimental work on the determination of barrier heights and the elucidation of the origin of barrier to internal rotation⁶. Although, the barrier heights have been measured most accurately by both theoretical as well as experimental methods, the elucidation of the origin of barrier is still eluding and remaining queerer and queerer and there is no unanimity among the scientists regarding this puzzling problem – the origin of the barrier to internal rotation⁷. However, Ghosh and Rahaman⁸ performed a density partitioning study on the problem of the origin of barrier following the formalism of Ruedenberg⁹ and demonstrated that the barrier to internal rotation does not originate from any new mysterious type of force, rather it develops from the forces and interactions responsible for molecular binding and anti-binding.

Molecular quantum mechanical calculations are quite suitable for molecular conformations which are not amenable to experiments, and for the transition states having fleeting existence. The molecular conformations and properties of electronically excited molecules can be well examined by theoretical methods while the geometries of such systems are often elusive experimentally. A theoretical model studying the process of molecular conformations should lead to an understanding of the physical meaning and origin of barrier and the factors affecting it. In order to understand the mechanism of development and origin, and also the magnitude of barrier to internal rotation, it is absolutely necessary to theoretically follow the process of evolution of molecular conformations as a function of reaction coordinates during such dynamic physical process of rotation of one part

of the molecule with respect to the other part. The pair of orbitals, HOMO and LUMO, are labeled as the frontier orbitals. The theoretical models having predictive success regarding the gross equilibrium molecular geometry and to follow the reorganization of molecular structure are : (i) Walsh rules¹⁰, (ii) symmetry rules of Pearson¹¹ and (iii) HOMO postulates of Deb¹². These theoretical efforts seem to provide a simple unifying principle in chemistry for understanding the structure and reactivity of molecules and have explored that the energetic behavior and the alteration in the electron population density distribution and the change of the symmetry type of the highest occupied molecular orbitals, HOMO, and the change in the symmetry type and the energetic behavior of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals, LUMO, on distortion of molecular structure largely determine the equilibrium shapes of the molecules. Fukui¹³ established that the frontier orbitals govern chemical reactions and solely determine the reaction path. Recent theoretical investigations have revealed that the height of the energy gap between the HOMO and LUMO is an important stability index for molecules and the most stable electronic structure has the largest HOMO-LUMO energy gap^{14,15}. It, therefore, follows according to the frontier orbital paradigm that when the geometry of a molecule transforms from equilibrium to non-equilibrium shape, its HOMO-LUMO gap decreases and the molecule becomes more and more unstable and chemically more reactive. On the other hand, when the molecule evolves from unstable non-equilibrium form towards the equilibrium shape, its HOMO-LUMO gap increases and becomes maximum at the equilibrium form. Ghosh *et al.*¹⁶ have recently found that the physical process of the evolution of molecular structure from the equilibrium shape to the transition state in the umbrella inversion of ammonia can be monitored by following the changes in the eigen values of the HOMO, the LUMO and the HOMO-LUMO gap of the molecule.

Density Functional Theory¹⁷⁻¹⁹ (DFT) is the most recent and powerful paradigm of quantum chemistry extensively used in studying the ground state electronic structure of many-electron systems and it has many important applications to chemistry. In addition to the calculation of electronic structure and properties of atoms and molecules, the DFT is used in elucidating and quantifying the familiar concepts of chemistry. The concept of hardness and the qualitative HSAB principle was introduced by Pearson²⁰. With density functional dressing, the HSAB principle has now been established as a very useful concept in the theory of electronic structure and reactivity of molecules. With the use of DFT as a basis, the hardness (η) of a chemical system has been rigorously defined and a new related funda-

mental property, the electronic chemical potential (μ) has been discovered and introduced²¹. The redefined and newly discovered important density functional parameters are the global hardness η , and the chemical potential μ . These are found to have extensive application in the field of molecular structure and are useful to study the comparative stability of different conformers. The profiles of chemical potential and hardness are found to have great importance in determining the behavior of systems and characterization of chemical reactions. It has been felt by several workers that η is an index of stability and chemical reactivity. Parr and Chattaraj²² showed that under the conditions of constant chemical potential and temperature, a chemical system evolves towards a state of maximum hardness or minimum softness. The softness is the inverse concept of hardness. This finding that increasing hardness is a measure of the movement of a system towards a more stable configuration, has been identified as the principle of maximum hardness, PMH²³. Pearson²³ considers the PMH as a rule of nature. When a system evolves towards a state of greater hardness, its stability increases, and when it evolves towards a state of lower hardness, its stability decreases. Pearson and Palke²⁴ demonstrated that the operation of PMH is fulfilled by the structural situation associated with the transition state (T.S.) in a chemical reaction, in inversion, asymmetric deformation, internal rotation, and many isomerization reactions. The hardness profiles of molecules have been computed by Chattaraj *et al.*²⁵ for the physical process of internal rotation, Datta²⁶, and Ghosh *et al.*¹⁶ for the phenomenon of structural inversion. Thus one concludes that it is the prediction of the new paradigm of quantum chemistry, the density functional dressed HSAB principle and the frontier orbital theory that when a molecule evolves from equilibrium to non-equilibrium structure its hardness (η) and the gap in energy of the frontier orbitals ($\nabla\epsilon$) will decrease and in the reverse process these quantities will increase and would be maximum at the equilibrium geometry. It is also established that the profiles of the above parameters can be theoretically computed to follow the structural changes in molecules caused by the physical processes of (i) inversion, (ii) deformation, (iii) internal rotation, and (iv) various types of simple reactions.

The new paradigm seems to usher a bright promise for better understanding the physical process of evolution of conformations of molecules and cast light on the mystery of the origin and development of the barrier to internal rotation. In order to explore the power of eigen values of the HOMO and LUMO, the HOMO-LUMO gap, the molecular orbital parameters and the global hardness, global softness and chemical potential, the density functional param-

eters to compute the physical process of the conformational isomerism of the molecules, we have taken up the frontier orbital and density functional study of the phenomenon of conformational isomerism of ethane.

The procedure of computation :

The hardness parameters—global hardness (η) and chemical potential (μ) are defined²¹ as

$$\mu = (\partial E / \partial N)_v \quad (1)$$

$$2\eta = (\partial\mu / \partial N)_v \quad (2)$$

where E is the energy, N the number of electrons, and v the potential due to fixed nuclei.

The other useful quantity global softness (S) is defined as

$$S = 1/\eta. \quad (3)$$

There is also an alternative definition of the above parameters coming from the calculus of variation¹⁹,

$$\mu = (\delta E / \delta\rho)_v \quad 2\eta = (\delta\mu / \delta\rho)_v \quad (4)$$

The use of δ in eq. (4) is read as 'the functional dependence of E and μ on ρ '.

The operational, and approximate definition of μ and η are

$$\eta = (I-A)/2 \quad -\mu = (I+A). \quad (5)$$

where I is the ionization potential and A the electron affinity of the system.

Koopmans' theorem can be used to further approximate and to write the working formula of μ and η in terms of the eigen values of HOMO and LUMO, the highest occupied and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals or the frontier orbitals of a molecule^{19,23},

$$-\epsilon_{\text{HOMO}} = I - \epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} = A \quad (6)$$

Hence the working formulae of η and μ are

$$\eta = (\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}})/2 \quad (7)$$

$$\mu = (\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} + \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}})/2 \quad (8)$$

The energy gap between the frontier orbitals, $\nabla\epsilon$, is

$$\nabla\epsilon = (\epsilon_{\text{LUMO}} - \epsilon_{\text{HOMO}}). \quad (9)$$

where ϵ_{LUMO} and ϵ_{HOMO} are the eigen values of LUMO and HOMO, respectively.

The coordinate system : The total energy of $\text{H}_3\text{C-CH}_3$ system is a function of as many as thirteen internal coordinates, viz. the length of one C–C and six C–H bonds, six,

<HCH angles and all the parameters are expected to vary with the dynamic evolution of the conformation of the molecule during the physical process of internal rotation of one part with respect to the other around the C–C single bond. However, the problem becomes enormously simplified because of the existence of symmetry in the molecule. Since the molecule follows the normal mode of vibration in the process of the evolution of geometry and in the symmetric mode of vibrations, all the six C–H bonds and all the six <HCH angles are equal, the actual number of variable geometric parameters remains to be only three – one C–H bond length, the C–C bond length and one <HCH angle. Theoretical methods studying the conformational isomerism are found to adopt two techniques, viz. (i) the rigid rotor (RR) model, and (ii) the geometry optimization technique (GOT). In the RR model, the geometric parameters are not varied and calculations are done with the same bond length and bond angles for all conformations. But in the GOT model, all geometric parameters are optimized at each stage of progress in the internal rotation of the molecule so that all the conformations can have optimized geometry. The GOT model seems to be more realistic and consistent with the dynamics of the evolving structures of molecules and has been adopted in the present investigation. The C–C bond is made coincident with the Z-axis and the C_{3v} symmetry of each CH_3 fragments is maintained in all the generated conformations by rotation of one CH_3 group around the Z-axis with respect to the other CH_3 . The feature of structural symmetry stated above permitted a great simplification in the determination of optimized geometry of each conformation and only three geometric parameters are needed to be optimized.

Whereas the conclusion of density functional theory is independent of the theoretical models and covers all levels of MO theories equally well¹⁹ and whereas the particular advantage of computation of eigen values of the frontier or-

bitals and density functional quantities in terms of the frontier orbitals by semi-empirical methods has been advocated²⁷ and whereas the Pople's CNDO method is quite efficient and well established for conformational studies²⁸, the CNDO/2 formalism of Pople and co-workers²⁹ is invoked in the present investigation. The standard parameters and STO basis set has been used for the computation.

The eclipsed conformation is chosen first and its geometric parameters are optimized. Thereafter staggering is started and one CH_3 part is rotated around the Z-axis by torsion with respect to the other CH_3 part and the geometric parameters of the new conformer are again optimized. The total energy, the density functional and molecular orbital parameters are computed for each conformer with optimized geometry. The process is cycled through steps of increasing the torsion through 10° dihedral angle and continued till the staggered conformation with the dihedral angle 60° is reached. The optimized geometric parameters as a function of dihedral angles is shown in Table 1. The total energy, the eigen values of the HOMO and LUMO and the HOMO-LUMO gap, and relevant density functional quantities are computed for each conformation and are shown in Table 2. In order to obtain the potential energy diagram of the molecule, the total energy is plotted as a function of dihedral angles in Fig. 1. The energy of each step of reorganization of the molecule generated through torsion about the C–C bond is plotted as a function of torsional angles in Fig. 2. The eigen values of the HOMO and the LUMO, gap in energy between the HOMO and the LUMO and the global hardness are plotted as a function of dihedral angles in Figs. 3 and 4, respectively. The global softness and the chemical potential are plotted as a function of torsional angles in Figs. 5 and 6, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reveals the general pattern of evolution of the

Table 1 Conformational analysis of ethane

The optimized geometric parameters and the total energy of the molecule as function of torsional angles

Torsional angles in degrees ($^\circ$)	<HCH angle in degrees ($^\circ$)	C–C bond length Å	C–H bond length Å	Total energy a u
0	106.3	1.464	1.12	-18.8218689
10	106.4	1.464	1.12	-18.8221283
20	106.4	1.464	1.12	-18.8227367
30	106.5	1.464	1.12	-18.8236332
40	106.5	1.464	1.12	-18.8245296
50	106.55	1.464	1.12	-18.8251839
60	106.65	1.464	1.12	-18.8254318

Table 2. Conformational analysis of ethane

The eigenvalues of HOMO and LUMO, the HOMO-LUMO gap (\mathcal{V}_e), the global hardness (η), the global softness (S), and the chemical potential (μ) as a function of torsional angles

Torsional angles in degrees (°)	ϵ_{HOMO} a.u.	ϵ_{LUMO} a.u.	$\Delta\epsilon$ a.u.	η a.u.	S (a.u.) ⁻¹	μ a.u.
0	-0.577094	0.2601105	0.8372046	0.418602	2.388902	-0.158492
10	-0.5772513	0.260432	0.8376833	0.418842	2.387537	-0.158410
20	-0.5775197	0.2606831	0.8382028	0.419101	2.386057	-0.158418
30	-0.5779973	0.2613810	0.8393784	0.419689	2.382716	-0.158308
40	-0.5783799	0.2617044	0.8400843	0.420042	2.380713	-0.158338
50	-0.5786577	0.2619402	0.8405979	0.420299	2.379259	-0.158359
60	-0.5788153	0.2622263	0.8410416	0.420521	2.378005	-0.158295

Fig. 1. Potential energy diagram of ethane molecule.

Fig. 2. Plots of the energy with the evolution of conformations as a function of torsional angles in ethane.

geometric parameters of the conformations evolving with the torsion around the C-C bond starting from the eclipsed conformation that the bond lengths are less sensitive while bond angles are more sensitive towards the physical process of dynamic structural isomerism occurring through the unrestricted rotation around single bonds. The length of the C-C bond remains virtually unaltered while the magnitude of $\angle\text{HCH}$ angle increases gradually but slowly with the beginning of the staggering and the trend continues up to the

Fig. 3. Plots of eigen values of HOMO and LUMO of ethane as a function of the torsional angles in ethane.

Fig. 4. Plots of the HOMO-LUMO gap and global hardness as functions of torsional angles.

evolution of the equilibrium or the minimum energy conformation, known as the staggered conformation in the terminology of conformational analysis.

From Table 1 it is evident that the total energy of the system is maximum at the eclipsed conformation and as soon as the torsion starts from the eclipsed form, the energy begins to decrease and as a natural consequence, becomes minimum at the staggered conformation. The computed energy of each stage of reorganization of structure obtained by pro-

gressive torsion of the molecule from the eclipsed form to staggered form is plotted in Fig. 2. Fig. 1 is the well-known potential energy diagram of the molecule. Fig. 2 is virtually a copy of the potential energy diagram of the molecule drawn in Fig. 1. However, Fig. 2 is more revealing so far as the energetics of evolution of conformational isomerism is concerned. The molecule exists in one of the three identical conformations in which the hydrogen atoms are staggered and which correspond to potential minima with respect to rotation about the C–C bond at the torsional angles of 60° , 180° and 300° . These potential minima or valley are separated by potential maxima or hills called energy barriers. The potential maxima correspond to conformations in which the hydrogen atoms are on top of each other called eclipsed conformations corresponding to torsional angles 0° , 120° , 240° and 360° . The computed barrier height is about $2.237 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ which is close to the most recent experimental value³ and the value obtained by more sophisticated *ab initio* calculations³⁰. This once again shows the power of the CNDO method in computing correct conformational isomers already noted by Gordon²⁸. It is evident from Fig. 2 that as the molecule evolves from the equilibrium staggered conformer, its energy increases steadily and becomes maximum at the eclipsed form. The effect of the evolution of conformations on geometric parameters transpires that, although the problem of the origin of rotation barrier is yet to be finally resolved, the non-bonded H---H interactions account for the major part of the barrier height and a possible mechanism of the origin of barrier¹⁶. We may venture to put forward a rationale of the observed variation of the geometric parameters of the molecule as a function of torsion. In the eclipsed form, the distance of separation between the non-bonded vicinal hydrogen atoms is minimum and hence interactions between such vicinal hydrogen atoms should be maximum. In order to relax the strain of repulsion between the non-bonded hydrogen atoms, the molecule reorganizes its struc-

ture by closing the <HCH angle thereby increasing the distance of separation between the non-bonded vicinal H-atoms. But as the torsion begins, the non-bonded repulsion starts decreasing and the molecule begins to relax. The consequence of the structural relaxation is that the <HCH angle widens and the trend continues till the staggered or equilibrium conformation is attained. Thus the geometric parameters of the molecule are reorganized in such a way during the movement of the molecule from equilibrium staggered conformation to the highest energy eclipsed conformation that the non-bonded steric strain is as minimum as possible.

Now let us study the conformational isomerism in terms of the computed density functional parameters. From Table 2 we see that with the very beginning of torsion from the eclipsed conformation, the energy of the HOMO starts decreasing and that of LUMO starts increasing gradually and the trend continues monotonically up to the staggered or minimum energy conformer when the eigen value of the HOMO is minimum and that of LUMO is maximum. Thus we see that as the molecular conformation evolves by a dynamic process of geometry reorganizations, the eigen values of the frontier orbitals vary continuously maintaining a regular trend with the dynamic evolution of molecular shape. The HOMO is most stable at the equilibrium conformation and most unstable at the eclipsed or highest energy conformation and the nature of variation of the eigen values of the HOMO in between these two extreme conformers is smooth and continuous. The LUMO, on the other hand, is most stable at the eclipsed form and most unstable at the staggered form and the nature of variation of the eigen values of LUMO is also continuous in between these two conformers, staggered and eclipsed. The position would be more revealing from the profiles of the eigen values of these two frontier orbitals drawn as a function of torsional angles. A close examination of Fig. 3 reveals that both the profiles of the HOMO and LUMO are periodic functions of the tor-

Fig. 5. Plot of the global softness as a function of torsional angles in ethane

Fig. 6. Plot of the chemical potential as a function of torsional angles in ethane

sional angles and nicely mimic the pattern of the potential energy curve of the molecule in Fig. 1. The phenomenon of the dynamic isomerism through the alternate cycle of staggering and eclipsing and the process of movement of the molecule from the highest energy eclipsed form to the minimum energy staggered form and also the reverse process of movement from the staggered form to the eclipsed form is nicely and distinctly reflected in the profiles of the HOMO and the LUMO. Thus, from the distinct isomorphism of the curves in Figs. 1 and 3, one may conclude that the eigen values of the frontier orbitals are equally reliable, like the total energy parameter, in studying the dynamic stereochemistry or the conformational isomerism of ethane molecule.

The theoretical models in their effort to correlate the equilibrium shapes of molecules in terms of some queer quantity seems to discover that the gross equilibrium molecular geometry is governed mainly by the behavior of the HOMO and the LUMO¹⁰⁻¹². Deb¹² relied on the electrostatic Hellmann-Feynman theorem. Pearson¹¹ relied upon the second order Jahn-Teller effect, the symmetry of the normal vibrations varying the molecular symmetry point group and the irreducible representations of the HOMO and LUMO. Walsh rule and diagram¹⁰ is simplest analysis available that shows the connection between molecular orbital theory and molecular geometry and relates molecular shape to the occupation of frontier orbitals. The present theoretical effort shows that the profiles of the energies of the HOMO and the LUMO of the conformations first obtained by torsion of one part with respect to the other part and then geometry reorganized through the normal mode of vibrations, can efficiently reveal the glimpses of the condition of stability of particular nuclear polyhedron and the physical process of the dynamic conformational isomerism can be followed by the profiles of eigen values of such frontier orbitals. We have recently observed the power of the energy profiles of the frontier orbitals in following physical process of the umbrella inversion of ammonia molecule¹⁶. Thus we can conclude that the dynamic conformational isomerism of molecules can be computed in terms of the eigen values of the frontier orbitals.

Now looking at Table 2 again we see that the energy gap between the HOMO and the LUMO, $\Delta\epsilon$ increases steadily with the beginning of torsion from the eclipsed conformation and increases monotonically with the progressive staggering and becomes maximum at the most stable conformation. The $\Delta\epsilon$ values along with the global hardness parameters, are plotted as a function of the torsional angles in Fig. 4. The role of the HOMO-LUMO

gap in predicting stability condition of the conformations becomes more revealing from the profile of $\Delta\epsilon$ as function of dihedral angles. Fig. 4 distinctly demonstrates that the profile of $\Delta\epsilon$ is monotone continuous between the two extreme conformers, the staggered and eclipsed forms. It is further revealed that, like the total energy parameter, $\Delta\epsilon$ is a periodic function of the dihedral angles of the rotational isomers and the profile of $\Delta\epsilon$ mimics the pattern of potential energy diagram in Fig. 1. Thus the profile of $\Delta\epsilon$ nicely and distinctly represents the phenomenon of the dynamic structural isomerism of ethane evolving through the alternate cycle of staggering and eclipsing of conformations. The nature of the profile of $\Delta\epsilon$ distinctly reveals the physical process of the evolution of structure of the molecule from the highest energy eclipsed form to the minimum energy staggered form and also the reverse process. The justification why the $\Delta\epsilon$ is a fundamental parameter for predicting the structural stability and reactivity of molecules was put forward by Pearson^{11,14,31,32} in terms of second order Jahn-Teller effect and quantum mechanical theory of response to a perturbation in a chemical system. It seems that so far the parameter $\Delta\epsilon$ has been extensively used in predicting the stability and reactivity of a particular nuclear polyhedron^{31,32}. We have recently found that $\Delta\epsilon$ values can be computed to follow the physical process of the umbrella inversion of ammonia¹⁶. The result tends to suggest that the HOMO-LUMO gap, $\Delta\epsilon$ is one more effective theoretical parameter for the study of the phenomenon of dynamic conformational isomerism of the molecules. Now let us consider the density functional parameters. From Table 2 we see that the global hardness η of the molecule is maximum at the staggered form and minimum at the eclipsed form and as the molecule evolves from the eclipsed form towards the staggered form, its global hardness increases, and in the reverse process of movement from staggered form towards the eclipsed form its global hardness decreases. Thus the nature of variation of the global hardness with structural evolution between the eclipsed and staggered forms is in accordance with principle of maximum hardness, PMH. The hardness profile of Fig. 4 shows that the nature of variation of the global hardness between the two extremums, the most stable staggered form and the most unstable eclipsed form, is monotone continuous and like the total energy parameter, it is a periodic function of the dihedral angles of the rotational isomers. Comparing the hardness profile in Fig. 4 and the potential energy diagram in Fig. 1 we see that the two curves are homomorphic. The condition of minimum energy is the condition of highest hardness and the condition of maximum energy is the condition of minimum hardness and the profiles of Figs. 4 and 1 are

mirror images. Thus the global hardness η has the potential ability to compute the dynamic process of conformational isomerism.

We have computed the global softness S , the inverse concept of global hardness through eqn. (3). From Table 2 we see that the global softness of the eclipsed form is maximum and that of the staggered form is minimum. From Fig. 5 we see that the profile of the global softness is monotone continuous between the two extreme conformers and is a periodic function of the dihedral angles. Comparing the curves of Figs. 1 and 5 it is at once evident that the softness curve is isomorphic with the potential energy curve. The periodic evolution of molecular conformations as a function of dihedral angles is nicely revealed in the softness profile of the rotational isomers. Thus, the global softness is also an equally effective parameter, like global hardness, for the study of the physical process of conformational isomerism. The chemical potential μ of the molecule is computed through the eqn. (8) and shown in Table 2. The DFT predicts that a more stable structure is associated with a higher value of η and lower value of μ . Although the PHM was derived under condition of constant chemical potential and temperature, some relaxation of restrictions are allowed and the PMH is found to be valid even if the conditions of constant μ and $v(r)$ are not satisfied. Looking at Table 2 and Fig. 6 we see that the nature of variation of the chemical potential is not monotonic but oscillatory between the most stable and unstable isomers. But it is to be noted that the chemical potential of the staggered form is highest and that of the eclipsed form is lowest. Thus we see that the chemical potential of ethane does not vary regularly with molecular conformations evolving through internal rotations. The chemical potential profile of the process of inversion of ammonia where the evolution of molecular shape takes place through the normal mode of vibrations¹⁶, is in accordance with the prediction of DFT. However, it may be mentioned that the conformational isomers of the instant case evolve through torsion first then reorganization of bond lengths and bond angles takes place through the normal modes of vibrations. Pearson and Palke²⁴ showed that the point groups of the molecules are determined by the maximum hardness, while the equilibrium bond angles and distances are determined by the electrostatic Hellman-Feynman theorem. However, we do not try to justify the nature of profile of the chemical potential as a function of torsion in the present report.

It is well known that shapes adopted by a polyatomic molecule actually depend on many factors and there is no simple theory of molecular shape that can take all the rel-

evant factors into account at once. Thus one of the most important contributions of DFT is to provide effective fundamental parameters, the global hardness η , the chemical potential μ , which have potential ability in computing and understanding the conformational phenomenon and to provide a sound picture of the origin of the conformational properties and effectively computing electronic changes accompanying conformational processes. The power of the molecular orbital theory to compute conformational isomers and accurate value of the barrier height is well known. A careful comparative study of the computed profiles of the HOMO, the LUMO, the HOMO-LUMO gap, the global hardness, the global softness vis-a-vis that of the total energy parameter explores that such molecular orbital and the density functional parameters are potentially effective to compute the conformational isomerism of molecules.

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